

Title: deep structures

1. PROGRAM NOTES

Sound composition using deep learning audio neural network training that explores with voice the implications of artificial intelligence from a transhackfeminist ethical perspective to act and think critically about these tools. In other words, as an algorithmic essay, the piece will explore the consequences of these technologies through voice, taking feminist and transfeminist research as a text that theorizes on the subject. The voice will be synthesized and reconstructed to hack into these networks and their understanding.

Fig. 1. deep structures visuals

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

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3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

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The piece is a performance in real time. Connections to the audio and video system are necessary. Two chairs and a table with space for two computers and a medium mixer are also necessary.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jxRiIYT-rmiyb-ofnCBEBqfryfCSjPD/view?usp=sharing>